

Title: Open Machine Learning Studio for Business Analytics with ActiveEon

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INTRODUCTION:

Considering the growth of Modern Big Data and Machine Learning, the ecosystems is becoming more and more multi-layered and heterogeneous. *To support custom needs, businesses are not considering a unique technology but an architecture of interconnected solutions that would bring value to a company.* Fortunately, most tech companies are now embracing open development, thus, supporting initial integration and setup through Rest API, SDK, CLI, GraphQL, etc. Then, managing diverse solutions and dependencies at scale quickly leads to new challenges for longer term control and governance.

AIM:

To control, orchestrate and automate these new environments, Activeeon developed *ProActive* to support business IT, sysadmins and data scientists.

MATERIALS:

ProActive Suite including: Open Machine Learning Studio, Resource Manager, Cloud Automation

METHODS/CONCEPTS:

The concepts followed by the team behind the ProActive solution are:

- Expressive and user friendly workflow studio to support any business user.
- Ease integration with an open solution (Rest API, CLI, SDK), an agnostic resource manger and by supporting users' preferred choice of language from bash scripts, to python through R.
- Simplified sharing and collaboration with building blocks and standard workflows.

- Granular control over execution through dashboards, error management, prioritization, etc.
- Building resource aware applications/jobs to improve utilization, reduce over provisioning and improve distribution.

RESULTS:

Stability through control and governance drive further innovation.

Resource consumption directly impact projects' ROI.

Visual dependency management for better control

Flexible and agile solution to drive more projects

Control and Govern execution to reduce Shadow IT, develop standard modules and incentivize further innovation.

CONCLUSIONS:

The complexity brought by Big Data and Machine Learning environment lead companies to focus more and more on control and governance while keeping resource consumption under scrutiny. ProActive from ActiveEon is an open source orchestrator and meta-scheduler balancing a need for agility with a need for greater control at scale.

KEYWORDS:

Open Studio, Machine Learning, AI, ROI, Flexibility, Granularity

BIOGRAPHY:

I am an experienced data scientist with Ph.D. degree completed in 2017 at University of Montréal (Canada) in particle physics on the ATLAS experience @ LHC. I have a broad range of experience in gathering, manipulating, and analyzing big volume data (TB) to gain insight into complex systems and to drive decision-making. I started to gravitate to the artificial intelligence field combined with Big Data tools in the industry during mid-2017. Since September 2017 I am a dedicated Data Scientist at Activeeon and I am glad to share my time between Paris and Montréal (Canada).